

On Photochemical Reaction between Bromine and Tartaric Acid in Aqueous Solution.

Part I

BY

JNANENDRA CHANDRA GHOSH

AND

JADULAL MUKHERJEE

Tartaric acid in bromine water yields hydrobromic acid, carbon dioxide and aldehydetartronic acid (Plotnikow, *Lehrbuch der Photochemie*, p. 576). This reaction was first studied in the dark by Bunsen and Roscoe (Ostwald's *Klassiker*, p. 92, No. 34, *Photochemische Untersuchungen von Bunsen und Roscoe*) who observed a very large period of induction as given in Table I below.

TABLE I

T(in hours)	18	20	42.5	88.5	163
$\frac{Bo-B}{Bo}$.01961	.02743	.05624	.43068	.62039

[(*Bo-B*) gives the bromine that has passed into a state of combination.]

The experimental results obtained in this investigation suggest that the reaction between bromine and tartaric acid in presence of light is a complicated one.

EXPERIMENTAL ARRANGEMENT.

Pure tartaric acid was further purified by recrystallisation and was dissolved in conductivity water to the required strength. Bromine used in these experiments

was carefully purified by first crystallising out Merck's extra pure bromine and distilling the molten crystals over potassium bromide. The solutions were kept in the dark in resistance glass vessels and were used up almost as soon as they were prepared. Experimental results with solutions which have been allowed to stand for some time were rather erratic and different from those obtained with fresh solutions.

The source of light was a 1000 c. p. Pointolite lamp, the strength of the current and the voltage of which was maintained constant by means of a regulating resistance. A parallel beam of light was obtained by placing a lens at its focal distance from the lamp. An absorption vessel 4 c.m. thick containing $N/50$ CuSO_4 solution and a Wratten monochromatic filter (blue) gave a pure blue light of wave-length limits between $450\text{-}490\mu\mu$. The reaction cell was placed inside a double-walled metal box provided with a window to admit light from the lamp. Through the annular space of the box, water from a thermostat was circulated by means of a pump worked with a hot air motor. The temperature within the box was maintained constant within $\pm 0.1^\circ$. Solutions of tartaric acid and bromine were first allowed to take up the temperature of the thermostat and were then mixed inside the reaction cell. The quantity of bromine was measured iodometrically, at intervals.

The intensities of the incident and transmitted lights were measured by noting the deflections of a very sensitive galvanometer connected with a Johansen thermopile, placed behind the reaction cell containing (1) pure water and (2) the reaction mixture. The difference gives the amount of light absorbed. The galvanometer and the thermopile were calibrated by a Hefner lamp, which according to Gerlach, gives on a sq. cm. at a distance of 1 metre 900 ergs per second.

The Dark Reaction.—The velocity of the dark reaction at temperatures below 40° was found to be too small to be taken into account in studying the velocity and mechanism of the photochemical reaction. The photo-decomposition of water by bromine is also too slow to affect the results given in this article.

Induction Period.—Table II gives the data for the progress of the reaction at its initial stages.

TABLE II.

Strength of the incident blue light=5400 ergs per sq. cm. per sec.

$C_{Br_2} = 0.0325 N.$

$C_{(tartaric)} = 0.0666 M.$

2 c.c. of the solution titrated against 0.00404 N thiosulphate solution.

Temp.=34°·3.

<i>t</i> in minutes	0	15	30	45	60	80	196	256	331
C c. of thio-sulphate soln.	16.1	16.1	15.95	15.45	15.1	13.8	10.5	9.5	8.4

Curve I in Fig. I gives the variation in concentration of Br_2 with time and in curve II the rate of transformation (not the velocity constant) is plotted against time. It will be seen that the rate of disappearance of bromine is at first very slow, reaches a maximum and then continually falls. For the descending limb of this curve, the reaction follows the unimolecular formula. This portion of the curve will be more thoroughly discussed later. No induction period was obtained when the reaction cell was exposed to intense sunlight or brought close to 1000 c. p. Pointolite lamp with only a water-filter interposed between. For incident light of average intensity,

however, a long induction period is always to be observed, which is practically independent of the concentration of either bromine or tartaric acid. These observations are in agreement with the classical experiments of Bunsen and Roscoe, who showed that for H_2 and Cl_2 mixture the induction period diminishes as the light intensity increases.

Table III gives experimental data, which enable the velocity constants corresponding to the descending limb of the curve to be calculated.

TABLE III.

Incident light intensity same as in Table II.

t	c.c. of thionl- phate.	Monomolecular k with conc. of Br_2 after 60 minutes' expo- sure as the initial concentration.	Monomolecular k with conc. of Br_2 after 150 minutes' exposure as initial concentra- tion.
0	—	—	—
80	28.1	.00082	—
150	28.7	.00077	.000688
210	21.55	.00074	.000693
285	19.1	.00073	.000694
360	16.95		

It was noticed that for this particular light intensity, the induction period and all other initial disturbances were over in 120-150 minutes and thereafter the disappearance of bromine followed a monomolecular equation.

In Table IV are tabulated the velocity constants for various reaction mixtures, the initial concentration of bromine used for calculating the constants being the

concentration existing after two hours' exposure to blue light of intensity 5400 ergs per sec. per sq. cm.

TABLE IV.

Temp.=34°·3.

Concentration of bromine in the original reaction mixture—0·0325 N.

Concentration of tartaric acid in the original reaction mixture	...	$\frac{2M}{3}$	$\frac{M}{3}$	$\frac{2M}{15}$	$\frac{M}{15}$
Monomolecular velocity coefficients	...	·0043	·00226	·00118	·00069

TABLE V.

Temp.=34°·3.

Concentration of bromine in the original mixture—0·0147 N.

Concentration of tartaric acid in the original mixture	$\frac{M}{3}$	$\frac{2M}{15}$	$\frac{M}{15}$	$\frac{2M}{45}$
Monomolecular velocity coefficients	·0126	·00525	·00278	·00186

In the photochemical reaction between bromine and tartaric acid, there are two components, tartaric acid and bromine, of which the latter is photo-active. According to Plotnikow (*Lehrbuch der Photochemie*, p. 185), the velocity of the reaction should be expressed by the following equation :

$$\frac{d(b-x)}{dt} = \frac{kI_0}{p} [1 - e^{-ip(b-s)}] (a-x) \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where a and b are the concentrations of tartaric acid and bromine respectively, I_0 the intensity of incident light and i the molecular extinction co-efficient. For very strong absorption equation (1) becomes

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = \frac{kI_0}{p}(a-x) \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

which is the equation for a monomolecular reaction. It is obvious that this equation, though monomolecular in form, cannot be applied to the experimental data for the simple reason that even when tartaric acid is in large excess compared to bromine (say, $M : \cdot 04 N$), a monomolecular constant is obtained; whereas if a is in large excess, $(a-x)$ is approximately constant and equation (2) transforms into a zero-molecular one.

For weak absorption of light, equation (1) becomes

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = kI_0 i(b-x)(a-x) \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

If a is in large excess, the reaction becomes unimolecular, but if b and a are comparable magnitudes, it retains its bimolecular character. If this equation were applicable it was to be expected that for large concentration of tartaric acid a monomolecular velocity constant would be obtained. The experimental results agree with this conclusion.

According to newer theories of the mechanism of a photochemical reaction, active molecules of the photo-active component are first produced by absorption of radiant energy. This activated molecule has a certain average life-period of excitation and if within this period, it can collide with an acceptor molecule, chemical transformation may occur. The probability of collision within the life-period of excitation (τ) will, in the cases of

gaseous systems, increase as the pressure of the acceptor gas molecules will increase, until for a very large concentration of the latter, all the activated molecules bring about chemical transformation by collision. The rate of chemical transformation for a constant rate of production of active molecules is given by

$$\frac{dc}{dt} = c \frac{\tau}{T + \tau} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

Cairo, *Zeit Physik.*, 1922, 10, 185.

Turner, *Phys. Review*, 1924, 23, 466.

If, however, the rate of production of active molecules is not constant, as in our experiments, the amount of radiant energy absorbed depends on the concentration of bromine, the above equation should be modified thus :

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dx}{dt} &= I_0 \left[1 - e^{-i(b-x)} \right] c \frac{\tau}{T + \tau} \\ &= (b-x)c' \frac{\tau}{T + \tau} \quad (\text{for weak absorption}) \end{aligned}$$

and the observed monomolecular velocity co-efficient,

$$k = c' \frac{\tau}{T + \tau} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (5)$$

Now the time period T between two successive collisions between an active bromine molecule and a tartaric acid molecule will, on the assumption that the kinetic theory of gases can be extended to dilute solutions, be given by the expression

$$T = \frac{1}{Aa^2p}$$

where

$$A = 2866 \cdot 6 \sqrt{\frac{2\pi N}{k\theta} \cdot \frac{m_1 + m_2}{m_1 m_2}}$$

a constant, a the distance between the centres of two reacting molecules on collision, and p the pressure of acceptor molecules expressed in millimeters of mercury (for solutions we may substitute osmotic pressure for gas pressure). It is obvious that in order that T should remain constant during the progress of the reaction, p should be kept constant. In our experiments tartaric acid was always in excess and its concentration remained practically constant. Then,

$$k = c' \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{Aa^2\tau p}}$$

$$\text{or } \frac{1}{k} = \frac{1}{c'} \left[1 + \frac{1}{Aa^2\tau p} \right]$$

$$= \frac{1}{c'} + \frac{1}{Aa^2\tau p c'} \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

Therefore $1/k$ plotted against $1/p$ should be a straight line. In Fig. 2 for curve II, where the initial concentration of bromine in the reaction mixture is $0.0147 N$, this is true, but for curve I (for higher initial concentration of bromine) the line obtained is not straight.

It is clear from curve II (Fig. 2) and equation (6) that

$$\frac{\text{Intercept}}{\text{Slope}} = Aa^2\tau$$

$$\text{Intercept} = 1.4, \quad \text{slope} = \frac{9}{28 \times 10^{23}} \times \frac{1}{p}$$

Now $A = 3.09 \times 10^{11}$ and if $a = 3 \times 10^{-8}$,

$$\tau \text{ becomes } 2.4 \times 10^{-11} \text{ seconds.}$$

For curve I (Fig. II) the value of the intercept is the same as in curve II indicating that for infinite concentration of tartaric acid, the velocity constants will be the same independent of the concentration of bromine, but the slope generally is much greater than that of curve I, and therefore the life period of active bromine molecules for the higher initial concentration of bromine is less than for lower concentrations. The diminution in the velocity co-efficient with increase in the initial concentration of bromine, is thus traceable to the diminution in the life period of active bromine molecules.

Photochemical After-effect.—A mixture of 10 c.c. of 0.0975 *N* bromine solution and 20 c.c. of *M*/15 tartaric acid solution was exposed to bright sun-light for 5 minutes and then kept in the dark at 30°. It was found that the reaction progressed in the dark with very large velocity to begin with ; but in almost an hour's time the reaction stopped altogether. If the solutions of bromine and tartaric acid are exposed separately to sunlight and then mixed together in the dark, this dark reaction does not take place. The data are given in Table VI and the graph for the rate of transformation against time is plotted in Fig. I (curve III).

TABLE VI.

After 5 minutes' exposure to sunlight.

<i>t</i> (in minutes.)	C. c. of thiosulphate.	$k = \frac{1}{t} \log \frac{a}{a-x}$
0	7.9	.028
15	6.9	.024
30	6.6	.023
45	6.45	.025
60	6.35	—

It is thus clear that a compound of bromine and tartaric acid is formed when exposed to light, the bromine of this compound being available for iodometric titration. The free bromine (*i.e.*, bromine not in a state of combination with tartaric acid) can be determined from curve III (Fig. I) and is equivalent to 6.3 c.c. of thiosulphate solution. The concentration of the bromine-tartaric acid compound is at any time equivalent to the thiosulphate titre at that time minus 6.3 c.c. The velocity co-efficients in the third column of Table VI have been calculated in this way. It will be seen that the velocity co-efficient of this dark reaction (0.025) is very large compared to the observed velocity of photochemical reaction under similar conditions of concentrations, but at 34.3° (0.00069, see Table IV). It thus appears that the mechanism of this reaction consists in the formation of an intermediate compound between bromine and tartaric acid under the influence of light, the velocity of this reaction depending on the concentrations of bromine, tartaric acid, temperature and the intensity of light as given in Eq. (6) and Tables IV and V. The bromine of this intermediate compound is available for titration iodometrically. This intermediate compound decomposes in the dark giving CO₂, HBr and aldehydetartronic acid, with a velocity constant very large compared with the velocity constant of the photochemical reaction in the first stage of transformation under the influence of the blue light of the intensity mentioned above. The theory of homogeneous consecutive reaction can, therefore, as usual, be applied to explain the observed period of induction.

*Application of Einstein's Law of Photochemical
Equivalence.*

It is obvious from the large induction period that the reaction is a very complex one, which would not conform

FIG. 1.

FIG. 2.

to Einstein's Law of Photochemical Equivalence. Still it was considered worthwhile to find out the total number of quanta that brings about the transformation of a molecule of bromine. The velocity of reaction, long after the induction period is over, should only be used for this calculation.

TABLE VII.

Temp. = 35°·3.

Initial bromine concentration = $N/67$.Concentration of tartaric acid = $M/3$.

2 c.c. of the reaction mixture titrated against $M/995$ thiosulphate solution.

t in. minutes	Quantity of thiosulphate required.
109	8.3
125	5
	} mean 6.65

Intensity of blue light just behind the reaction vessels containing pure water is $\frac{5.6}{14} \times 900$ ergs per sec. per sq. cm.

Intensity of blue light just behind the reaction vessel filled with bromine solution, 2 c.c. of which = 6.65 c.c. of $M/995$ thiosulphate solution is $\frac{80.41}{14} \times 900$ ergs per sec. per sq. cm.

Hence, quantity of light absorbed per sq. cm. per sec. is $\frac{5.59}{14} \times 900$ ergs.

No. of quanta of blue light of average wave-length 470 $\mu\mu$,

$$= \frac{5.6}{14} \times 900 \times \frac{470 \times 10^{-7}}{6.55 \times 10^{-11} \times 3 \times 10^{10}}$$

No. of molecules of Br_2 transformed per c.c. (the reaction vessel was 1 cm. thick) per second.

$$= \frac{3.3}{2} \times \frac{6.17 \times 10^{18}}{990 \times 1000} \times \frac{1}{16 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{\text{No. of molecules}}{\text{No. of quanta absorbed}} = 12 \text{ (approx.)}$$

We have already seen that if the initial concentration of bromine is increased, the reaction velocity diminishes. It was found that for initial concentration of 0.0325 N bromine and of $2M/3$ tartaric acid the ratio of

$$\frac{\text{No. of mols}}{\text{No. of quanta}} = 4 \text{ (approx.)}$$

Velocity of Reaction in Plane Polarised and Circularly Polarised Light.

Tartaric acid is an optically active compound, and it was thought probable that the velocity of photo-bromination might not be dependent only on the intensity of light. A large nicol (4 sq. cm. in aperture) was used for obtaining the plane polarised light, whose intensities could be varied by using lenses of different focal lengths. A Fresnel Rhomb, interposed between the nicol and the reaction cell, gave circularly polarised light when the plane of polarisation of light incident normally on the face of the Rhomb, is at an angle of 45° to the horizontal cross-section of the Rhomb. To counteract the disturbing action, if any, of the film of Canada balsam on the nicol, the velocity of photo-bromination in ordinary light was also measured with a film of Canada balsam between two optical glass plates placed in front of reaction vessel.

	Divisions of Galvanometer	Velocity Constant.
Intensity of parallel beam of ordinary light -	170	0.00489
Intensity of polarised light -	172	0.00493
Intensity of circularly polarised light -	155	0.0045

It thus appears that the velocity constant depends only on the intensity of light and is independent of the state of polarisation of the light.

Temperature Co-efficient of the Velocity of Reaction.

The majority of photochemical reactions have very small temperature co-efficients; in fact if Einstein's law were strictly correct the velocity should be independent of temperature. As Table VIII will show, the temperature co-efficient of this reaction is between 1.7 and 2.

TABLE VIII.

Temp.	Initial conc. of bromine.	Initial conc. of tartaric acid.	Velocity constant.
34°-3	.0825N	M/15	.0069
24°-3	"	"	.0040
34°-3	.0137N	"	.00284
24°-3	"	"	.0014.

Tolman (*J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 45, 2285) has suggested a way out of this difficulty. He considers that molecules in the lower quantum state may not be in a condition to absorb radiant energy of the frequency used, or the energy level which they attain after the absorption

may not be high enough to lead to chemical reaction and obtains the relation

$$\frac{d \log K \text{ (velocity const.)}}{dT} = \frac{\bar{E} - \bar{E}}{kT^2}$$

where \bar{E} is the average energy before activation of those molecules only which pick up radiant energy and react, and \bar{E} is the average energy of all the molecules. If $\bar{E} - \bar{E}$ is zero, the temperature co-efficient is unity but if $\bar{E} - \bar{E}$ has a large value, the temperature co-efficient will be correspondingly large.

THE UNIVERSITY,

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DACCA.

Varying Valency of Platinum with respect to Mercaptanic Radicles.

Part II.

BY

SIR PRAFULLA CHANDRA RAY

AND

KSHITISH CHANDRA BOSE RAY.

It has already been shown that platinum in relation to certain mercaptanic radicles behaves as di-, tri-, tetra-, penta-, hexa- and octa-valent respectively (Ray *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 133). In the present communication further evidence is brought forward in support of this view.